

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

CONSIDERATION OF ENVIRONMENTAL CONDITIONS IN THE TOURISM INDUSTRY

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Abstract

The tourism sector of Georgia has a great potential. In the recent period, the development of the regional tourism industry has become particularly relevant. For the development of regional tourism, it is necessary to define the marketing strategy of the country, through which the market opportunities of this or that field are revealed. The economic impact of tourism, its impact on the social and natural environment, taking into account the principles of sustainable development, the need to deepen the studies of the state of tourism and development prospects. Conditions that allow to comprehensively solve the problems related to the survival of the local population, the protection of natural resources and cultural heritage.

The development of tourism is greatly influenced by the climate, which is an important factor in travel and recreation around the world. Similarly to tourism resources, the climate is also changing. Therefore, it is not known how favorable the effects of climate change will be for the tourism industry. Therefore, the climate will not be under the control of people, so the tourism industry must adapt itself to the characteristics of the air produced as a result of the processes taking place on earth.

Keywords: Sustainable tourism, tourist resource, climate, tourist flow

Tourism is one of the fastest growing and most profitable sectors of the world economy. The tourism industry contributes to job creation and income growth, economic diversification, environmental protection, promotion of historical and cultural values and bringing cultures closer together. Accordingly, tourism is one of the priority sectors of economic development of the country.

The influence of the external world is not the same everywhere, therefore, when considering the impact of environmental conditions on tourism, it is important to identify the most essential factors of environmental impact and to develop effective ways of influencing them. Economy and tourism closely influence each other. In addition, tourism is interconnected with such social systems as economy, ecology, social environment, politics, technology and others. Although there is very high competition in the field of tourism in the world market, the development perspective of the Georgian tourism industry is quite optimistic.

The functioning of the tourist market and related industries has a pronounced seasonal character, which is affected by many factors. The primary factors of the functioning of the tourist market are natural-climatic, and the secondary factors are economic, demographic, psychological, technological and others. The World Meteorological Organization (WMO) has implemented a number of measures to support tourism. It provides the World Tourism Organization (WTO) countries with early warnings about natural disasters, glacier retreat, water resources and climate change. Forecasts of climate and extreme hydrometeorological events, provided by national hydrometeorological services, are especially important in today's conditions, since regional climatic variations have emerged in the background of global climate change.

Thus, it can be said that in the tourism business, in the evaluation of tourist-recreational resources, both

from the ecological and economic point of view, a full-fledged study of the impact of the environment and climate is one of the relevant issues.

The development of the resort-tourism industry directly depends on the geographical location, topography, vegetation, weather and climate of the given region. Weather and climate are the two main factors that determine the bioclimatic resources of a place. Therefore, many countries pay great attention to the investigation of these resources, which are necessary for the organization and development of the resort-tourism industry. Climate affects tourism both directly and indirectly. In the tourism sector, climate is essential for tourists. Unfavorable climatic conditions and their changes can affect the tourist flow or the seasonal change of tourist activities. The seasonality of tourism and changes in the consumer sector, which are due to climatic variations, affect tourism-related sectors as well. The study of seasonality in the field of tourism allows to determine the degree of influence of natural and climatic conditions on the formation of the tourist product, to identify the factors that determine seasonality in tourism, to develop a system of measures to reduce the inequality of seasonality.

Tourism object consists of three main parts: tourist institution, tourist service organization and tourist region. While traveling, the tourist has the right to use the service complex provided to him in a specific place or region. On the other hand, due to the attractive conditions, these places are the center of tourism.

During the trip, the tourist chooses a tourist route, during which he compares both the natural conditions of the tourist place and the level of service. A product ordered or purchased by a tourist consists of a service offered to a tourist in a particular tourist region. The tourist region should have a tourist center, where appropriate material and technical base will be created for

accommodation and recreation of tourists. In the tourism industry, there are several issues of defining a tourist region, which is closely related to the definition of the following issues: How can the area that a tourist chooses to travel be defined, which is chosen by different market sectors. The World Tourism Organization (WTO) defines a tourist region that has a wide network of services. On the other hand, a service network for the tourist region is needed for the organization of recreation and health. Therefore, a tourist region is a place that has a material and technical base and at the same time can provide services to tourists.

A tourist region is a travel destination and a tourism product. In addition, it is necessary to take into account the derivation of this definition from the interests of the user. Along with this, the decisive factor is the geographical area, which should benefit the tourist. In most cases, the selection of such territories violates political boundaries. When selecting a tourist region, the interests of the vacationer should be taken into account, during which four main parameters are distinguished: place, landscape, accommodation and excursions. Regional tourism consists of two main aspects: geographical and socio-economic. The geographical aspect reflects the territorial distribution of recreational resources, the means of attracting tourists to the given territory, while the socio-economic aspect shows the utilization of the recreational resources of the territory, which determines the place of the given region in the tourist market.

The first approach represents the possibilities of tourism development, and the second represents the result of the tourism activity of the given region. Therefore, the tourist region is evaluated both by the holiday organizers and by the local or arriving vacationer. One of the important tasks of the region as a separate unit is to maintain competitiveness for a long time. The competitiveness of the region is influenced by the interaction of various industries and their markets, as well as the population and the outside world. The implementation of tourism projects is facilitated by the local population, which is favorable towards tourism. Regional tourism is a prerequisite for the development of farming, which is characterized according to the following main directions:

- 1) tourist routes and its structure;
- 2) peculiarities of tourism in a specific region;
- 3) types and forms of tourism;

4) specificity of tourism policy and attitude of tourist organizations;

5) economic role of tourism in the economic structure of the region;

6) prospects of tourism development in the given region. Tourism and agriculture represent the prospective directions of Georgia's economy. Tourism as a service sector has a special place in the development of the world economy. The positive aspects of the development of tourism in Georgia are the growth of the economy, the reduction of the unemployment level, and the historical and cultural popularization.

Conclusion

Thus, tourism is of great importance for the development of the country's economy, and the potential of tourism resources is a prerequisite for the development of tourism. Interest in Georgia has existed since ancient times, since it is one of the outstanding countries in terms of resource potential. It has great potential for resort activities due to its geographical, climatic, recreational opportunities and historical-cultural heritage. The geographical location of the district plays a big role in the development of tourism. It should be noted the proximity to the sea, mountain and forest massifs and the features of the coastline. The presence of tourism resources in the region is an important prerequisite for the development of the tourism industry, and the development of regional tourism is influenced by economic and social factors.

References:

1. Evaluation of tourist-recreational resources against the background of climate change. A. Amiranashvili, L. Megreldze, L. Kurdashvili, Tbilisi – 2019
2. Amiranashvili A., Amiranashvili V., Kartvelishvili L., Nodia Kh., Khurodze T. Influence of Air Effective Temperature and Geomagnetic Storms on the Population of Tbilisi City. *Trans. of the Institute of Hydrometeorology*, vol. 115, ISSN 1512-0902, Tbilisi, 18 – 19 November, 2008a, pp. 434–437, (in Russian)
3. Amiranashvili A., Chargazia Kh., Matzarakis A., Kartvelishvili L. Tourism Climate Index in the Coastal and Mountain Locality of Adjara, Georgia. *International Scientific Conference “Sustainable Mountain Regions: Make Them Work”*. Proceedings, Borovets, Bulgaria, ISBN 978-954-411-220-2, 14-16 May, 2015c, pp. 238-244, <http://geography.bg/MountainRegionsSofia2015>